

NON LINEAR BEHAVIOR OF TWO WOVEN CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

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SUMMARY: The non-linear mechanical behavior of both a 2D SiC-SiC and a 2D C-SiC woven ceramic matrix composites is investigated under cyclic loading by means of a metrology coupling an ultrasonic method and classical strain measurements. It appears that the loss of stiffness during monotonous loading is mainly due to transverse microcracks density and that the changes in elasticity during cyclic loading are the result of the opening/closure of these cracks. In order to take this effect into account, an internal variable that represents the damage accumulated along the loading is introduced. The non linear behavior of both materials is predicted under both monotonous and cyclic loading. The constitutive laws of the crack density and opening/closure variable describe the three-dimensional changes in elasticity under cyclic loading as well as the inelastic strains along the whole test.

KEYWORDS: microcracking, anisotropic damage, ceramic matrix composites, cyclic loading, inelastic strains

INTRODUCTION

The non-linear behavior of ceramic matrix composites (CMC) has been extensively studied under monotonous loading [1]. Concerning cyclic loading, the knowledge is mostly concentrated on cyclic fatigue and frictional sliding determination. It is now commonly recognize that the macroscopic behavior of these materials under tensile loading is the result of the combination of three main damage mechanisms [2]: the matrix microcracking normal to the tensile axis, the deflection of these cracks at the fiber-matrix interface if the interface is weak enough and the fibers fracture. The matrix microcracking induces a loss of stiffness. The Mode II cracking prevents the composite from failing too early. The fiber-matrix debonding leads to a fiber-matrix sliding with friction depending on the nature of the interface. The interfacial shear stress is thus of first importance in the global behavior. The combination of these mechanisms leads to a highly non linear behavior.

The stress-strain curves of these materials clearly show that the global strain is the sum of an elastic and an inelastic strain. The inelastic strain comes from both the opening of the transverse cracks and the interfacial fiber-matrix sliding [3]. Nevertheless this sliding is subordinate to the direction of the load. Assuming the damage is the relative variation of the stiffness tensor [4], it appears that the damage does not increase, or slightly, during the cycles. The value of damage reached during monotonous loading is the upper limit of

damage during the cycles. When a cyclic loading is performed, as the stress decreases during unloading, a sliding opposite to the one created by an increase in stress can occur. The transverse cracks that have been created during the monotonous loading are then prone to close (Fig. 1). They are still present anyway but their closure simulates an increase of stiffness as if the material could recover its mechanical properties. The cracks that remain open represent the active part of the microcracking. The sample exhibits an apparent state of damage while the damage accumulated is greater.

Fig. 1: States of the transverse cracks: (a) Open crack, (b) Close crack

In order to separate and to identify accurately the effects of the initiation and growth of matrix microcracks under tensile loading as well as the effect of these cracks under cyclic loading on both the stiffness and the inelastic strains, it is necessary to perform a strain partition under load.

FORMULATION OF THE MODEL

With the cracked media replaced by an effective equivalent medium, it is possible to deduce the variations of the elastic properties of the cracked material. By modeling the cracks as elliptic cylinders; $x_1^2/a^2 + x_2^2/b^2 = 1$, $|x_3| < \infty$, the effective elastic properties of a fibrous composite containing cracks are [5]:

$$S = S_0 + \frac{\pi}{4} \beta \Lambda \quad (1)$$

where S is the compliances tensor of the material, S_0 is the compliances tensor of the uncracked material, Λ is a fourth order tensor which terms depend upon both the cracks whose aspect ratio $\delta=b/a$ tends to zero and the mechanical properties of the medium that surrounds them and β is the crack density. Cracks thickness $2b$ in Direction 3 is considered as negligible. Length $2c$ in Direction 2 is higher than depth $2a$ in Direction 1.

Thus, the damage due to a single damage orientation can be described with one parameter only: the crack density. This formulation was written for a single crack system. Actually the degradation process exhibits several specific orientations. It is very common to observe three

orthogonal crack systems in CMC; a transverse one due to matrix cracking, a longitudinal one due to fiber-matrix debonding as well as an interlaminar one when delamination occurs [6]. It is also important to keep in mind that these systems might interact. For the transverse crack system, normal to the tensile axis, only three components of Λ are different from zero [7]: Λ_{33}^T , Λ_{44}^T and Λ_{55}^T . As the cracks are deviated in mode II in the fiber-matrix interphase, a longitudinal crack system with crack density β_L must be taken into account. For this longitudinal crack system, parallel to the tensile axis, the non zero components of the crack tensor Λ^L are obtained by a simple index transformation: Λ_{22}^L , Λ_{44}^L and Λ_{66}^L . When delamination occurs, the interstacks cracks that appear are modeled by a family of slit cracks parallel to Plane (2, 3) and normal to Axis 1. The crack density is β_L . We then have for the crack tensor Λ^I : Λ_{11}^I , Λ_{55}^I and Λ_{66}^I .

As a proportion of the transverse cracks can close during unloading, it is necessary to differentiate an apparent state of cracking and the number of cracks that have been created effectively [8]. The closing effect induces a damage deactivation leading to unilateral behavior [9]. Obviously, the crack density parameter is very sensitive to the effect of the opening/closure of the cracks. Just as the active cracks were defined, we can define an active crack density:

$$\beta = F \cdot \beta^* \quad (2)$$

where F is the proportion of active cracks and β^* is the density of cracks that have been accumulated. F represents the proportion of cracks that remains open during unloading.

Taking into account the phenomenon of opening-closure of the cracks, assuming that the effects of the various cracks systems are additive and adding a corrective term that takes into account their interaction, the compliance tensor of the cracked material becomes:

$$S = S_0 + \frac{\pi}{4} F_T \cdot \beta_T^* \Lambda^T + \frac{\pi}{4} F_L \cdot \beta_L^* \Lambda^L + \frac{\pi}{4} F_I \cdot \beta_I^* \Lambda^I + S^{interaction} \quad (3)$$

Thus, the global behavior depends upon six functions: β_i^* and F_i ($i=T,L,I$). The compliances variations are then simply a function of the various cracks systems that appear through the variations of the crack densities and of the mechanical properties of both the uncracked and damaged material. When cyclic loading is performed, the opening/closure functions F_i modulate the compliances variations.

The inelastic strains represent a large part of the total strains in CMC. It is now commonly recognized that they mainly come from the crack opening displacements, in other words, the cracks thicknesses. In an extensometer length L , if there are n cracks, $2a$ deep and $2b$ thick, the distance between them is $2a/\beta_T^*$. So:

$$n = L \beta_T^* / 2a, \quad (4)$$

and then:

$$\varepsilon^{inelastic} = \Delta L^{inelastic} / L = n U / L = n 2b / L = \delta \beta_T^* \text{ where } \delta = 2b / 2a \quad (5)$$

During unloading, the effect of closure of the cracks must be taken into account. It is clear as well that some cracks will not close completely, some have a residual thickness. This thickness is most probably due to the roughness of the cracks edges coming from both wear debris at the sliding interfaces and wedging of the cracks by grain bridging. That is why another aspect ratio δ' that takes this new thickness into account is introduced. Finally, the variations of inelastic strains during the whole test can be described by:

$$\epsilon^{inelastic} = \beta_T^* (F(\delta - \delta') + \delta') \quad (6)$$

The inelastic strains are thus a function of the transverse crack density and of the aspect ratio of the cracks whether they are completely open or not. As for the compliances, the opening/closure function modulates the inelastic strains variations during cyclic loading.

The opening of the cracks is strongly correlated to the sliding stress that takes place at the fiber/matrix interface. The measurement of the inelastic strains and the identification of the transverse crack density had lead us, with the help of a modified shear lag model [10], to establish a new formulation to identify the interfacial sliding stress τ :

$$\tau = RE_f \left(\left(\alpha / \beta_T \right) \epsilon^{anelastic} - \epsilon^{elastic} \left(\left(l/8 \right) - \left(b^2 / 2l \right) \right) \right) \left((l/2)^2 - b^2 \right)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Eqn (7) simply relates τ to the radius of the fibers R , their Young modulus, E_f , the distance between the cracks, l and the length along which the interface remains bonded, b (Fig. 1 (a)).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to study accurately the damage evolution in composites, an experimental device that couples an ultrasonic immersion tank associated to a tensile machine and an extensometer has been developed. It allows to study the loss of stiffness of the material under tensile stress because it makes it possible to perform under load the angular investigation necessary to identify the elastic tensor variation. As it gives access to the complete stiffness tensor, it becomes possible to know which coefficients are affected during the damage [11]. It also allows to know precisely which proportion of the global strain is either elastic or inelastic [12].

Fig. 2: Under load strain partition equipped sample

The characterization of anisotropic materials using an ultrasonic method gives access to the purely elastic part of their behavior. The main principles of ultrasonic evaluation have been given by Roux [13] for the elastic coefficients evaluation of homogeneous anisotropic materials. The nine elastic constants C_{ij} which fully describe the elastic behavior of an orthotropic material are identified by the wave propagation velocities in three data planes: Plane (1, 2), Plane (1, 3) and Plane (1, 45°) described by the bisectrix of axis 2 and 3 (Fig. 2) [14].

The two composites studied, a 2D SiC-SiC and a 2D C-SiC, are of woven type. They are manufactured from preforms built up from multiple layers of respectively Silicon Carbide and Carbon cloth by S.E.P. (Société Européenne de Propulsion, France). The SiC matrix was in both cases added by chemical vapor infiltration. Under tensile stress, they exhibit rapidly a non linear behavior mainly due to the matrix microcracking. Because of the woven nature of the samples, Directions 2 et 3 are initially symmetrically equivalent. Both specimens are thin plate shaped, 3 mm in thickness and 2.7 g.cm^{-3} in density. They were submitted to tensile stress in Direction 3 parallel to one of the bundle direction.

The stress-strain curves of the samples are shown on Fig. 3 and 4. Although the strain to failure is about 0.8 per cent for the two composites studied, they reach this value in a different manner. The 2D C-SiC exhibits quite immediately a non linear behavior whereas the 2D SiC-SiC remains elastic until about 80 MPa as the linear variation of the strain testifies. About the cycles performed, the lack of hysteresis in the 2D C-SiC curve is relevant of the fact that the sliding occurs with little or no friction in the fiber-matrix interface whereas the large loops with many changes in slopes that appear in the curve of the 2D SiC-SiC are relevant of the interfacial debonding extent and emphasize the presence of sliding with friction that needs a threshold of stress to occur. But in both cases, the permanent strains are far from negligible. It is noteworthy that, until 120 MPa, the stress-strain curve of the 2D SiC-SiC shows that the strain increases during the steps necessary for the ultrasonic evaluation while the loading device is constant stress controlled.

Fig. 3: Stress-Strain Curve of a 2D SiC-SiC

Fig. 4: Stress-Strain Curve of a 2D C-SiC

The accuracy and the reliability of the complete determination of the stiffness tensor together with its variation during the test allow, by inverting this tensor, to get the tensor of elastic compliances and its own variation. The variation of all the components of the compliance tensor of the 2D SiC-SiC with their confidence interval is shown in Fig. 5. The compliances variations exhibit three domains. Until 70 MPa, damage threshold of this composite, the various compliances remain the same. From then, the matrix microcracking begins. The compliances increase along the tensile axis is very large; S_{33} increases more than 300%. This represents the increase in compliance due to the inter-bundles matrix cracks until saturation at

about 120 MPa. Then, this variation becomes slighter as the matrix microcracking spreads inside the bundles. The shear moduli related to the planes that include the tensile axis, S_{44} and S_{55} , also increase a lot. The microcracking affects more slightly the elastic coefficients in Plane (1, 2) normal to the cloth plane.

Fig. 5: Comparison between experimental data and predicted evolution of the compliances $((1000.GPa)^{-1})$ of a 2D SiC-SiC.

Fig. 6 shows the variations during the cycles of the compliances of the 2D C-SiC that were the most influenced by the damage with their relative confidence intervals. The cycles are shifted for clarity. S_{33} , S_{44} and S_{55} relative to the transverse cracks system are the only compliances to exhibit a variation during the cycles. S_{11} does not vary at all during the whole test and nor S_{66} nor the off diagonal compliances, S_{12} , S_{13} and S_{23} . S_{22} varies during the monotonous loading but do not change along the cycles. The progressive variation of S_{33} , S_{44} and S_{55} during the cycles points out a progressive closure of the cracks. As the cracks close, they are active no more and they lose the effect they had on the stiffness constants. When the sample is reloaded, the cracks re-open, become active again and every compliance reaches the value it has before unloading.

The elastic strains are obtained with the generalized Hooke's law:

$$\varepsilon_i^{elastic} = (C_{ij})^{-1} \sigma_j = S_{ij} \sigma_j \quad (8)$$

Therefore the elastic strain along the tensile axis is simply S_{33} times the applied stress. As an extensometer indicates the total strain, the inelastic strain is then obtained simply:

$$\epsilon^{inelastic} = \epsilon^{total} - \epsilon^{elastic} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 6: Comparison between experimental data (o) and predicted evolution (—) of the most influenced compliances ($(1000.GPa)^{-1}$) of a 2D C-SiC.

Fig. 7 and 8 show respectively the relative part of the elastic and inelastic strains on the total strain during the monotonous loading of the 2D SiC-SiC and of the 2D C-SiC. Fig. 8 also shows what happen during the cycles in the 2D C-SiC. In both cases, the inelastic strains are far from negligible. Unlike the 2D C-SiC, the strain partition of the 2D SiC-SiC exhibits three zones during monotonous loading. If for the 2D SiC-SiC, the inelastic strains do not appear until the beginning of the inter-bundles matrix microcracking, it is clear that they are present from the very beginning of the test in the case of the 2D C-SiC. There is no damage threshold for the 2D C-SiC whereas the behavior remains linear elastic until about 80 MPa for the 2D SiC-SiC.

The inelastic strains of the 2D SiC-SiC exhibit two very different increases that correspond to the scale at which they occur; an increment of strain at constant stress $\Delta\epsilon_{bs}$ which starts around 80 MPa and stops at about 140 MPa due to inter bundles microcracking and a strain ϵ_{fs} which needs an increase in stress and which begins at 120 MPa when the cracking starts to occur at the fibers scale inside the bundles. The strain partition on the cycles of the 2D C-SiC indicates that the linear variation observed is the sum of the non linear variation of both the elastic strain and inelastic strains. As it could have been awaited for, the elastic strain comes back to zero when no stress is applied whereas the inelastic strains are still present in the form of residual strains.

This emphasizes that the strain measured when the sample is fully unloaded represents only the residual part of the inelastic strain because the reversible sliding has closed some of the cracks. It is noteworthy that the residual strain value at the unloading point is far smaller than the under load inelastic strain. This establishes the partly reversible nature of the inelastic strain and therefore the necessity of doing the strain partition under load.

Fig. 7: Under load strain partition of a 2D SiC-SiC

Fig. 8: Under load strain partition of the 2D C-SiC with a cyclic loading at 280 MPa

IDENTIFICATION OF THE MODEL

The experimental variations of the elastic constants and Eqn (1) give access to the constitutive laws of the cracks density, Fig. 9 and 10. Only the monotonous loading is necessary to identify the crack densities. From the variations of the compliances of both samples, it results that every cracks density variation exhibits a linear behavior, the transverse variation having the greatest slope whatever the material and the scale considered. The interlaminar crack density β_I of the 2D C-SiC does not vary during the test meaning that no or very small delamination occur between the stacks for this sample. The fact that the two longitudinal cracks systems display a more stochastic behavior indicates that these damage mechanisms may be more influenced by local variations of the composite microstructure. About the 2D SiC-SiC, up to 80 MPa, as the damage has not begun, the crack densities are equal to zero. Then, at the inter-bundle scale, a 10 MPa delay necessary for the mode II cracking to start is highlighted.

During monotonous loading, all the transverse cracks are open. So the opening/closure function F is equal to 1. Eqn (2) reduces to:

$$\beta_T = \beta_T^* \quad (10)$$

The comparison between the experimental data and the predicted variations are depicted in Fig. 5 and 6. For the 2D SiC-SiC, a good correlation is obtained for the first three diagonal compliances, S_{11} , S_{22} and S_{33} . The three remaining ones, S_{44} , S_{55} and S_{66} , exhibit a more or less large deviation between the predictions and the experimental results. Anyway, concerning the inter-bundle part of the cracking, up to about 120 MPa, the predictions for S_{44} and S_{55} are good. For S_{66} , the deviation probably indicates that the transverse cracks thickness must be taken into account in the model. In the intra-bundle part of the prediction of the shear moduli, the deviations might be explained this way: first, as the crack systems are not independent, they might interact and second, one of the hypothesis of the model is that the cracks are elliptic, but, actually, at the intra-bundle scale they are more likely to be circular because their extent is limited by the fibers arrangement. This is emphasized by the similar variation of S_{44} and S_{55} in the intra-bundle part. Finally, concerning the off-diagonal compliances, the remark about taking into account the transverse cracks thickness is also valid to improve the prediction. For the 2D C-SiC, the comparison between the experimental data and the predicted variations shows a good correlation for the monotonous loading represented by the top of the cycles.

Clearly, during loading-unloading cycles, only the mechanism of the opening/closure of the transverse microcracks will take place. The state of the longitudinal and interstacks cracks does not, or slightly, vary. Thus the model of compliance variation can be simplified:

$$F_L = 1 \quad \beta_L^* = \beta_L \quad \text{and} \quad F_I = 1 \quad \beta_I^* = \beta_I. \quad (11)$$

Fig. 9: Cracks densities of a 2D SiC-SiC under tensile loading.

Fig. 10: Cracks densities of a 2D C-SiC under tensile loading.

At the top stress of a cycle, σ_{max} , all the cracks are open. We get the maximum of active cracks and thus, $F=1$. At zero stress, there is still a non zero proportion of open cracks leading to residual strains. F is minimum but different from zero as all the cracks do not close.

On Fig. 11 is represented the opening/closure variable F of the 2D SiC-SiC. This step function is representative of the existence of the threshold of stress needed to begin the fiber/matrix sliding at the interface. Fig. 12 shows the evolution of F during the various cycles of the 2D C-SiC. The proportion of open cracks can be described by a unique scalar function describing the progressive opening /closure of the transverse cracks:

$$F = 1 - ((1 - r)/(1 + r))^m \quad \text{where} \quad r = (Y_0 + Y)/(Y_0 + 1) \quad \text{and} \quad Y = \sigma/\sigma_{max} \quad (12)$$

where $Y_0 = -0.25$ is the threshold where all the cracks close and $m = 1.2$ a constant.

So, for this material, the behavior during the cycles is fully described by four functions: β^*_T , β^*_L , β^*_I and F that can predict the compliances variations (Fig. 6).

The inelastic strains prediction (Fig. 13) during both monotonous and cyclic loading is rather good as well once the residual opening of the cracks of the 2D C-SiC has been taken into account (Eqn (6)). Fig. 14 describes the evolution of the inelastic strains for the 2D SiC-SiC at the various scales of its behavior as a function of the two transverse cracks densities and the aspect ratio using Eqn (5). A 10 MPa delay for the sliding to begin can clearly be seen. However, there is a gap between the experimental data and the prediction at the end of the inter-bundles phenomenon because the two slidings coexist in a 40 MPa range.

About the 2D C-SiC, micrographs have indicated that the material contains a lot of porosities and that many transverse cracks are situated in the SiC mantel around the bundles. The opening/closure of these cracks certainly occurs without any friction because the opening takes place on the pore side. This can explain the lack of hysteresis during the cycles. The interfacial shear stress of the 2D SiC-SiC has been identified to be about 27 MPa using Eqn (7) at the inter bundle scale and much higher at the fibers scale. This is in line with the assumption of a strong cohesive zone inside the bundles.

Fig. 11: Opening-closure variable for transverse microcracks of a 2D SiC-SiC

Fig. 12: Opening-closure variable for transverse microcracks of a 2D C-SiC.

Fig. 13: Evolution of the inelastic strains during cyclic loading of a 2D C-SiC.

Fig. 14: Evolution of the inelastic strains of a 2D SiC-SiC.

CONCLUSION

The behavior of ceramic matrix composites is strongly influenced by matrix microcracking. The ultrasonic characterization through the complete determination of the stiffness tensor along the whole test can detect all the damage mechanisms of CMC: the transverse matrix microcracking as well as the presence of longitudinal cracks at the fiber-matrix interface. Thus this technique is of great help in measuring the anisotropic damage and it also allows to perform the strain partition under load which is the only way to separate the various damage mechanisms. This technique gives a correct estimation of both the inelastic strains and the elastic modulus drop. The problem of the three-dimensional description of the non linear behavior of ceramic matrix composites can be solved by the measurement of the cracks

density parameters and the closing-opening variable. Their knowledge can fully predict the loss of stiffness due to matrix microcracking responsible for the non linear behavior of CMC. These parameters, representative of the initiation and growth of the cracks, describe the elastic part of the behavior. Furthermore, with the estimation of the cracks aspect ratio, the inelastic strains can be predicted accurately.

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